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20.	समकालीन कला और उपभोक्तावाद अर्चना गर्ग	87
21.	गीत गोविन्द में भक्ति भावना की अभिव्यक्ति कविता भटनागर	90
22.	राष्ट्रीय अर्थव्यवस्था के विकास में लघु व कुटीर उद्योगों का योगदान शिल्पा जैन, कमलेश	92
23.	स्वातंत्र्योत्तर गजल गायकी पर रागों का प्रभाव, जुगलबन्दी और शास्त्रीय रागों में निबद्धता प्रतिभा सक्सेना	97
24.	भारतीय राजनीति में गुट और गुटबन्दी की भूमिका मंजू बघेल	100
25.	प्राचीन भारत में श्रेणी संगठनों का कौशल विकास (Skill Development) में योगदान सागर पुरी	103
26.	ग्रामीण सामाजिक संरचना में परिवार की भूमिका अशोक कुमार सिंह	109
27.	माध्यमिक स्तर पर योगाभ्यासी एवं गैरयोगाभ्यासी विद्यार्थियों की व्यक्तित्व आवश्यकताओं का तुलनात्मक अध्ययन गरिमा शर्मा, धीरज कुमार रस्तोगी	112
28.	Role of Globalization on Market : A Village Study of Western U.P. Vinita Lal	118
29.	Role Of Community Based Health Intervention In Transformation of Rural Women: A Progress Towards Achieving Millennium Development Goal Shalini Singh	123
30.	Women Entrepreneurship In South Asia: A Subordinate Proposotion Mohd. Israr Khan	130
31.	Public Participation in the Ancient Indian Atatecraft Anil Kumar Singh	138
32.	Women Empowerment In India : Primitiveness Of The Reformists And Economists T.B. Singh, Akansha Singh	141
33.	DNA Test as Forensic Evidence "A Legal Analysis" Sailesh K.Singh	152
34.	Impact of Mobile Phone on Youth Krishna Kumar	158
35.	Assessing Identity of Karbi Tribes: A Case Study of Assam Jayanta Doley	160
36.	The PGW Culture in Garhwal Region; A Comparative Study with North Western Sites of Ganga Yamuna Doab Priya Saxena	166
37.	Attitude of Graduate Students Towards ICT and Its Applications Nandini Kashyap	173
38.	A Study of Achievement Motivation Level of Arts Students at Secondary Level Sikandra Ali	179

Impact of Mobile Phone on Youth

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Youth plays a very crucial and significant role in our society. The growth and development of country depends on youth. Youths are most significant and basic elements of our population composition and society. Youth plays functional role in development of country. If youths have multidimensional personality and development growth of multi dimensional personality is depends on culture of society. Thus, the personality of youth can be refined by culture. If the culture has been changed through any process, youth are affected by its. The mobile is the part of our culture .Undoubtly youths are effected this culture. Youths of today are the nation of tomorrow. The most cursory look at any modern society reminds us that it is composed of many communities friendship, family ,work and other types of group which have an internet structure of their own. Every society has status system. The most pervasive of which is social class; youth class significantly determines the social environment and power of individual. Since its mainly through face to face relation that a person`s behavior is influenced by his fellows motive cued rewarded and punished by social control. Openness of status system to vertical social mobility is determined by functional requirement of society, mobile has both positive and negative consequence for the youth.

Modern age is the age of science. Science has made many wonderful inventions. Mobile phone is one of them. Mobile phones these days it has become very popular and its popularity is

increasing day by day. Martin Cooper(2012)1, said that mobile was very useful for human being. Mobile phone also support a wide variety of other services such as text messaging, MMS, E-mail, Internet access, short range wireless communication, business application, gaming and photography. Thus increasing use of mobile phone will help us a lot to make progress in every field of activity. The youths today is an extremely technology- savvy one, a segment of society that has been active in transforming the application & use of digital technologies in unprecedented ways. The segment here defined as the range of teenagers& youths between of 12-29 is more comfortable with using Internet. According to Scottadate(2012)2, younger user has fast adoption curve & a strong desire to stay connected to friend, although they tend to be prone to handset fods, and long term prospect for immovable features are uncertain. Andrew (2012)3 defined that mobile phone uses for various purposes, wheather, job, business, schoole and others. It is also used for education. Marples Gareth (2012)4, says his book that mobile phone is part of culture of society with the help of mobile technology we can do our work in business education and others.

The study "Impact of mobile phone on youth class". As sociological study was based on Kanpur District. The aims & objectives of the study is to analyse the Impact of mobile phone on human health , its role in human society, impact on youth and his deviant behavioral activities. In

this study. out of 28000, 100 respondent has been taken on the basis of Random sampling method .

During the survey, researcher had collected some facts regarding education level of respondent. Only 2% are professional degree and 42% respondent have done Intermediate level. In this study 10% respondents are between way of communication and means of entertainment , while 80% respondents preferred both options . Important role of mobile in human lives, is that 4% respondents are between by communication and maximum population of respondents *i.e.* 70% all of them from of age using mobile phone, 60% respondents are between 20-23 age group. 72% respondents accept mobile as a social problems and 28% respondents saying no about social problems. 76% respondents accept, human body effected by mobile phone. Impact of mobile phones on youth class in society, shows that maximum population of respondents *i.e.* 64% select both option. During the survey, surveyor tries to know the status of respondents, it has been found that development via phone of Indian Society,76% respondents reply in affirmative.

During the survey, surveyor had collected some facts regarding business via mobile phones 84% respondents have preferred yes. Increasing crime by mobile phones data shows that 34%

IMPACT OF MOBILE PHONE ON YOUTH

respondents are between No, and maximum populations of respondent(64%) shows yes. By mobile phone we can get global information ,14% respondents are between No and 86% respondents are between yes.

During the survey it has also been found that mobile phone is a way of earning, 16% respondents are between No, while 84% respondents are between yes. Mobile phones are tremendous source of education, communication and entertainment. 94% respondents are between yes. It has been found that via mobile phones unemployment can be reduce when 38% respondents between No, while 62% respondents have indicated yes.

Thus, Youths are effected by mobile phones in all dimensions including social, cultural, economical, mental as well as physical context.

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